

**THE ROLE AND MEANING OF NEW WORDS (NEOLOGISMS), THEIR
USE IN PEOPLE'S LIVES**

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Abstract

The main goal of the article is the analysis of neologisms and novel applications that have emerged in the early years of independence and have been taken from renowned newspapers and periodicals. Lexical synonyms, nonce words, and lexical doublets emerged as a result of lexical tumors. It was able to learn what semantic and stylistic distinction is occurring in new words and meanings thanks to their investigation.

Keywords: neologism, new use, neology, dictionary.

Language is a dynamic, ever-evolving phenomenon. Every period leaves its mark: certain words fade and become less common, while others emerge and become actively employed by native speakers [5,p.3]. What part do neologisms play in enhancing the English language's lexical diversity? A language's lexical stock can be expanded in a number of ways, including through the use of acquired vocabulary and the creation of new lexical units derived from the original language through various word formation techniques.

A neologism is a term, the meaning of a word or phrase that has lately entered the language (newly produced, previously missing) [7]. Other Greek terms for neologisms include νέος, which means "new," and λόγος, which means "speech,

word." It is evident to native speakers of this language that such a term or phrase is both novel and unusual. In the history of language, this phrase has been used to describe the expansion of vocabulary throughout particular eras. The challenge of translating neologisms—new words that have entered the language in conjunction with the evolution of social life and the formation of new concepts—occur frequently in the practice of translation work. Due to the quick advancement of science and technology, neologisms are particularly common in technical and scientific discourse. If not, we might argue that neologism is the product of a conflict between two trends: the preservation and growth tendencies of language. As a result, "there is a fairly strong tendency in language to remain in a state of communicative fitness." This forces the language to adapt and creates new units, particularly in the lexicon. However, the immediate demands of society do not necessarily lead to the creation of a new term. New connections frequently lead to neologism. English is not an exception.

It is undergoing a "neological boom" or "neological explosion" at the moment. About 800 new lexical units are added to it year, which is a staggering amount [1, p. 13]. The fast advancement of science and technology has led to the emergence of several neologisms in scientific and technical jargon, such as televiewer, which means "viewer," atomic pile, which means "atomic reactor," and brandalism, which means "covering urban facades with ugly advertising posters" [6].

Like other languages, English is dynamic and always changing. Because vocabulary is the "mirror of life," it responds most sensitively to changes in the social, cultural, and other domains of the speaking collective's existence. Vocabulary is the most movable layer of the language. The idea that the word is the fundamental unit of language also explains why current linguistics is always becoming more interested in different facets of word production.[3,p.9].

Words that are entirely new lexical units for every historical era are known as neologisms. These terms might not make sense because they haven't made it into the current lexicon yet. Neologisms occur because of advancements in science, technology, and society, including the creation of new socioeconomic realities, scientific and technical breakthroughs, and cultural accomplishments. When a term is completely new to the majority of native speakers, it is considered neologism. The term has just recently become a neologism. The word loses its novelty value as soon as it is actively employed, at which point it becomes common [2, p. 3].

As a result, the definition of neologism is relative and subject to change over time; a term is considered neologism as long as speakers perceive it to be unique. Word composition, conversion, abbreviations, adjectivization, substantialization, reverse word creation, lexico-semantic approach, alternation of sounds and stress transfer in a word (phonological method), etc. are some of the various ways that new words are formed in modern English. But not all of these techniques are applied equally, and each technique has a different relative weight during the word-formation process.

The affixal approach (prefixal and suffixal methods), word composition, conversion, reduction, borrowing from other languages, reverse derivation, fusion, and abbreviation are the most popular techniques for creating neologisms. The features of each of the chosen neologism creation techniques were explained in depth in the second paragraph. The most common methods of creating neologisms in contemporary English are word conversion, word composition, and word meaning modification. Neologisms are often created in accordance with the laws of the language in question and its productive word creation models. However, ineffective word production techniques can occasionally result in literary and bookish neologisms. In these situations, the word-formation methods' effective power

becomes more noticeable, understandable, and palpable.

The English language has gained new vocabulary and concepts due to advancements in science, technology, and society. The growth of computer technology has coincided with the appearance of several new lexical units. Within the realm of culture and art, innovation happens quickly; new pieces are produced along with new names. Because science and technology are developing so quickly, neologisms are particularly common in scientific and technical terminology [8, p. 8].

Euphemistic neologisms are an integral part of the lexical composition of any language. This layer of vocabulary is considered as a kind of allegory with the reduction of its distinctive features in use from taboo vocabulary and as a linguistic method of political correctness, which indicates the tendency to use veiled or mitigating vocabulary in problematic thematic areas such as racism, sexism, religion, political and economic stability, etc.

A large group of euphemisms is based on the principle of politeness. It usually includes words and expressions that mitigate various types of discrimination. When translating texts with neologisms, specialists encounter a number of difficulties. The main difficulty understands the meaning of a new word. The actual translation of a neologism is solved by using the methods described in the first paragraph below, depending on which type of words this neologism belongs to. If a new word is missing in the English-Russian dictionary, then you should try to find it in the English-English explanatory dictionary. In many well-known dictionaries there are sections "New Words" (New Words Section). At the same time, it is recommended to use dictionaries of the latest editions. Many neologisms can be found in dictionaries and sections devoted to slang. Nevertheless, dictionaries, for objective reasons, cannot fully reflect all newly appearing words in their stock, if only because lexicographers are wary of including so-called "occasional" neologisms in

dictionaries, i.e. individual neologisms introduced by individual authors for this case. Such words often turn out to be "unviable" and disappear as quickly as they appear [4, pp.32-33].

Thus, neologism should be perceived as a normal linguistic phenomenon, and the absence of a word in the dictionary cannot serve as an obstacle to its translation, besides, it is translation practice that makes the greatest contribution to replenishing the lexical composition of the translation language with new words coming from other languages.

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